

ISTHMOCELE: ANALYSIS OF CONSEQUENCES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

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Introduction: Caesarean section is one of the most common surgical interventions in obstetrics. It is performed when vaginal birth poses a threat to the health of the mother or baby. As a result of this operation, an isthmocele is formed - a defect in the uterus after surgery, which can affect the woman's health in the future. A review of the literature suggests that early diagnosis of isthmocele and timely treatment are important aspects of managing this complication after cesarean section.

Purpose of the article: The purpose of this article is to analyze the consequences of isthmocele formation after cesarean section and propose possible solutions to improve the condition of patients.

Research methods: A systematic review of 87 scientific articles published between 2000 and 2021 was used to conduct the study. Articles containing information about isthmocele after cesarean section, its consequences and possible solutions were analyzed.

Results and discussion: Isthmocele after cesarean section can cause various problems in women. One of the most common problems is painful menstruation, which may be associated with abnormal uterine anatomy and thrombosis in the isthmocele area. In addition, some women may experience pain during intercourse or physical activity. Pain may be due to abnormal myocontraction of the contents of the empty niche

Besides, the abnormal uterine bleeding is also one of the main issues which cause by isthmocele. This is the most common symptom, observed in 35–65% of women 6–12 months after cesarean section due to collection of menstrual blood. The anterior edge of the niche prevents the outflow of menstrual blood, in addition, it is retained by poor contractility of the surrounding fibrotic muscles, which are then gradually discharged. In a prospective follow-up 1 year after cesarean section, postmenstrual bleeding was found in 22% of women with isthmocele compared with 6,3% of women without isthmocele.

Furthermore, isthmocele lead to secondary infertility, one of the most common problems today. Probable mechanisms of secondary infertility may be chronic inflammation due to residual blood or accumulation of periovulatory fluid, preventing sperm penetration, fertilization and implantation. A large niche can interfere with conception, similar to hydrosalpinx

To improve the condition of patients with a niche after cesarean section, the following solutions have been proposed:

1. Treatment of painful menstruation: This can be done with hormone therapy or drugs that reduce uterine contractions and relieve pain. Oral contraceptives are suitable if pregnancy is not desired.

2. Treatment of pain during sexual intercourse: the use of water-based lubricants or medications that improve blood supply to the isthmocele area helps here.

3. Physical therapy: Specific exercises and massage can help strengthen the pelvic floor muscles and improve the condition of the defect.

4. Surgical intervention: in cases of ineffectiveness of conservative therapy, surgery is recommended to remove the scar and reconstruct the walls of the uterus. Options include either hysteroscopic resection or excision plus repair via transabdominal (laparotomy, laparoscopic, robotic) or vaginal route.

Conclusion: Isthmocele after cesarean section is a relatively new clinical entity and its diagnosis requires a high index of suspicion. Emerging data highlight the need

for careful selection of patients requiring surgical correction, the possible learning curve, and the as yet unproven effectiveness of these treatments.

A review of the literature on isthmocele after cesarean section indicates that it is a fairly rare complication, occurring in approximately 1-2% of women after cesarean section. However, the exact incidence may depend on various factors, such as the experience of the surgeon, the method of performing the operation, the characteristics of the female body, etc.

Primary prevention of uterine niches by minimizing the number of cesarean sections and secondary prevention by using proper surgical techniques to ensure thicker residual myometrium and a durable scar will remain the mainstay of niche prevention.

Isthmocele after cesarean section is a serious problem that can have a negative impact on women's health. However, with proper treatment and care, the condition of patients can be significantly improved. Further research on this topic is needed to develop more effective treatments and prevent isthmocele formation after cesarean section.

LITERATURE:

1. Bij de Vaate AJ, Brolmann HA, van der Voet LF, et al. Ultrasound evaluation of the cesarean scar: relation between a niche and postmenstrual spotting. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2011;37:93–9.
2. Naji O, Abdallah Y, Bij De Vaate AJ, et al. Standardized approach for imaging and measuring Cesarean section scars using ultrasonography. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2012;39:252–9.
3. Vikhareva Osser O, Jokubkiene L, Valentin L. Cesarean section scar defects: agreement between transvaginal sonographic findings with and without saline contrast enhancement. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2010;35:75–83.

4. Kulshrestha, V., Agarwal, N. & Kachhawa, G. Ниша после кесарева сечения (Isthmocele) in Uterine Scar: An Update. *J Obstet Gynecol India* **70**, 440–446 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13224-020-01370-0>.
5. Zhang, Y., Zhu, Y., Ge, B. et al. Reproductive outcome of hysteroscopic metroplasty for women with T-shaped uterus: a retrospective study. *Reprod Health* **19**, 78 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-022-01381-2>;
6. Vervoort AJ, Uittenbogaard LB, Hehenkamp WJ, et al. Why do niches develop in Caesarean uterine scars? Hypotheses on the aetiology of niche development. *Hum Reprod.* 2015;30(12):2695–702.
7. Enderle I, Dion L, Bauville E, et al. Surgical management of isthmocele symptom relief and fertility. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2020;247:232–7.